

A Study on Fractional Fourier Series of Four Types of Matrix Fractional Functions

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Abstract: In this paper, based on a new multiplication of fractional analytic functions, we find the fractional Fourier series of four types of matrix fractional functions. Matrix fractional Euler's formula and matrix fractional DeMoivre's formula play important roles in this article. In fact, our results are generalizations of ordinary calculus results.

Keywords: New multiplication, fractional analytic functions, fractional Fourier series, matrix fractional functions.

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent decades, the applications of fractional calculus in various fields of science is growing rapidly, such as physics, biology, mechanics, electrical engineering, viscoelasticity, control theory, modelling, economics, etc [1-15]. However, the rule of fractional derivative is not unique, many scholars have given the definitions of fractional derivatives. The common definition is Riemann-Liouville (R-L) fractional derivative. Other useful definitions include Caputo fractional derivative, Grunwald-Letnikov (G-L) fractional derivative, and Jumarie type of R-L fractional derivative to avoid non-zero fractional derivative of constant function [16-20].

In this paper, based on a new multiplication of fractional analytic functions, we use some methods to obtain the Fourier series expansions of the following four types of matrix fractional functions:

$$\begin{aligned} & \sin_{\alpha}(r\cos_{\alpha}(tAx^{\alpha})) \otimes_{\alpha} \cosh_{\alpha}(r\sin_{\alpha}(tAx^{\alpha})), \\ & \cos_{\alpha}(r\cos_{\alpha}(tAx^{\alpha})) \otimes_{\alpha} \sinh_{\alpha}(r\sin_{\alpha}(tAx^{\alpha})), \\ & \cos_{\alpha}(r\cos_{\alpha}(tAx^{\alpha})) \otimes_{\alpha} \cosh_{\alpha}(r\sin_{\alpha}(tAx^{\alpha})), \\ & \sin_{\alpha}(r\cos_{\alpha}(tAx^{\alpha})) \otimes_{\alpha} \sinh_{\alpha}(r\sin_{\alpha}(tAx^{\alpha})), \end{aligned}$$

where $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, r, t are real numbers, and A is a real matrix. Matrix fractional Euler's formula and matrix fractional DeMoivre's formula play important roles in this article. In fact, our results are generalizations of traditional calculus results.

II. PRELIMINARIES

At first, we introduce the definition of fractional analytic function.

Definition 2.1 ([21]): If x, x_0 , and a_n are real numbers for all n , $x_0 \in (a, b)$, and $0 < \alpha \leq 1$. If the function $f_{\alpha}: [a, b] \rightarrow R$ can be expressed as an α -fractional power series, i.e., $f_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha}) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} (x - x_0)^{n\alpha}$ on some open interval containing x_0 , then we say that $f_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha})$ is α -fractional analytic at x_0 . Furthermore, if $f_{\alpha}: [a, b] \rightarrow R$ is continuous on closed interval $[a, b]$ and it is α -fractional analytic at every point in open interval (a, b) , then f_{α} is called an α -fractional analytic function on $[a, b]$.

In the following, a new multiplication of fractional analytic functions is introduced.

Definition 2.2 ([22]): Let $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, and x_0 be a real number. If $f_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ and $g_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ are two α -fractional analytic functions defined on an interval containing x_0 ,

$$f_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} (x-x_0)^{n\alpha}, \quad (1)$$

$$g_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{b_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} (x-x_0)^{n\alpha}. \quad (2)$$

Then we define

$$\begin{aligned} & f_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha g_\alpha(x^\alpha) \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} (x-x_0)^{n\alpha} \otimes_\alpha \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{b_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} (x-x_0)^{n\alpha} \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} \left(\sum_{m=0}^n \binom{n}{m} a_{n-m} b_m \right) (x-x_0)^{n\alpha}. \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Equivalently,

$$\begin{aligned} & f_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha g_\alpha(x^\alpha) \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_n}{n!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} (x-x_0)^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha n} \otimes_\alpha \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{b_n}{n!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} (x-x_0)^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha n} \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n!} \left(\sum_{m=0}^n \binom{n}{m} a_{n-m} b_m \right) \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} (x-x_0)^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha n}. \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Definition 2.3 ([23]): If $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, and $f_\alpha(x^\alpha)$, $g_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ are two α -fractional analytic functions defined on an interval containing x_0 ,

$$f_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} (x-x_0)^{n\alpha} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_n}{n!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} (x-x_0)^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha n}, \quad (5)$$

$$g_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{b_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} (x-x_0)^{n\alpha} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{b_n}{n!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} (x-x_0)^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha n}. \quad (6)$$

The compositions of $f_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ and $g_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ are defined by

$$(f_\alpha \circ g_\alpha)(x^\alpha) = f_\alpha(g_\alpha(x^\alpha)) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_n}{n!} (g_\alpha(x^\alpha))^{\otimes_\alpha n}, \quad (7)$$

and

$$(g_\alpha \circ f_\alpha)(x^\alpha) = g_\alpha(f_\alpha(x^\alpha)) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{b_n}{n!} (f_\alpha(x^\alpha))^{\otimes_\alpha n}. \quad (8)$$

Definition 2.4 ([24]): If $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, and $f_\alpha(x^\alpha)$, $g_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ are two α -fractional analytic functions defined on an interval containing x_0 ,

$$f_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} (x-x_0)^{n\alpha} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_n}{n!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} (x-x_0)^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha n}, \quad (9)$$

$$g_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{b_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} (x-x_0)^{n\alpha} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{b_n}{n!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} (x-x_0)^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha n}. \quad (10)$$

The compositions of $f_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ and $g_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ are defined by

$$(f_\alpha \circ g_\alpha)(x^\alpha) = f_\alpha(g_\alpha(x^\alpha)) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_n}{n!} (g_\alpha(x^\alpha))^{\otimes_\alpha n}, \quad (11)$$

and

$$(g_\alpha \circ f_\alpha)(x^\alpha) = g_\alpha(f_\alpha(x^\alpha)) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{b_n}{n!} (f_\alpha(x^\alpha))^{\otimes_\alpha n}. \quad (12)$$

Definition 2.5 ([25]): If $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, t is a real number, and A is a matrix. The matrix α -fractional exponential function, matrix α -fractional cosine function, and matrix α -fractional sine function are defined as follows:

$$E_{\alpha}(tAx^{\alpha}) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (tA)^n \frac{x^{n\alpha}}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n!} \left(tA \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^{\alpha} \right)^{\otimes_{\alpha} n}, \quad (13)$$

$$\cos_{\alpha}(tAx^{\alpha}) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (tA)^{2n} \frac{(-1)^n x^{2n\alpha}}{\Gamma(2n\alpha+1)} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{(2n)!} \left(tA \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^{\alpha} \right)^{\otimes_{\alpha} 2n}, \quad (14)$$

$$\sin_{\alpha}(tAx^{\alpha}) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (tA)^{2n+1} \frac{(-1)^n x^{(2n+1)\alpha}}{\Gamma((2n+1)\alpha+1)} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{(2n+1)!} \left(tA \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^{\alpha} \right)^{\otimes_{\alpha} (2n+1)}. \quad (15)$$

In addition, the matrix α -fractional hyperbolic cosine function and matrix α -fractional hyperbolic sine function are defined as follows:

$$\cosh_{\alpha}(tAx^{\alpha}) = \frac{1}{2} [E_{\alpha}(tAx^{\alpha}) + E_{\alpha}(-tAx^{\alpha})] = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (tA)^{2n} \frac{x^{2n\alpha}}{\Gamma(2n\alpha+1)} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n)!} \left(tA \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^{\alpha} \right)^{\otimes_{\alpha} 2n}, \quad (16)$$

and

$$\sinh_{\alpha}(tAx^{\alpha}) = \frac{1}{2} [E_{\alpha}(tAx^{\alpha}) - E_{\alpha}(-tAx^{\alpha})] = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (tA)^{2n+1} \frac{x^{(2n+1)\alpha}}{\Gamma((2n+1)\alpha+1)} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n+1)!} \left(tA \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^{\alpha} \right)^{\otimes_{\alpha} (2n+1)}. \quad (17)$$

Theorem 2.6 (matrix fractional Euler's formula)([26]): If $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, $i = \sqrt{-1}$, and A is a real matrix, then

$$E_{\alpha}(iAx^{\alpha}) = \cos_{\alpha}(Ax^{\alpha}) + i \sin_{\alpha}(Ax^{\alpha}). \quad (18)$$

Theorem 2.7 (matrix fractional DeMoivre's formula)([27]): If $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, p is an integer, and A is a real matrix, then

$$[\cos_{\alpha}(Ax^{\alpha}) + i \sin_{\alpha}(Ax^{\alpha})]^{\otimes_{\alpha} p} = \cos_{\alpha}(pAx^{\alpha}) + i \sin_{\alpha}(pAx^{\alpha}). \quad (19)$$

III. MAIN RESULTS

In this section, we obtain the Fourier series expansions of four types of matrix fractional functions by using some methods.

Theorem 3.1: Suppose that $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, r, t are real numbers, and A is a real matrix. Then

$$\sin_{\alpha}(r \cos_{\alpha}(tAx^{\alpha})) \otimes_{\alpha} \cosh_{\alpha}(r \sin_{\alpha}(tAx^{\alpha})) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{(2n+1)!} r^{2n+1} \cos_{\alpha}((2n+1)tAx^{\alpha}), \quad (20)$$

$$\cos_{\alpha}(r \cos_{\alpha}(tAx^{\alpha})) \otimes_{\alpha} \sinh_{\alpha}(r \sin_{\alpha}(tAx^{\alpha})) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{(2n+1)!} r^{2n+1} \sin_{\alpha}((2n+1)tAx^{\alpha}), \quad (21)$$

$$\cos_{\alpha}(r \cos_{\alpha}(tAx^{\alpha})) \otimes_{\alpha} \cosh_{\alpha}(r \sin_{\alpha}(tAx^{\alpha})) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{(2n)!} r^{2n} \cos_{\alpha}(2ntAx^{\alpha}), \quad (22)$$

$$\sin_{\alpha}(r \cos_{\alpha}(tAx^{\alpha})) \otimes_{\alpha} \sinh_{\alpha}(r \sin_{\alpha}(tAx^{\alpha})) = - \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{(2n)!} r^{2n} \sin_{\alpha}(2ntAx^{\alpha}). \quad (23)$$

Proof Since

$$\begin{aligned} & \sin_{\alpha}(rE_{\alpha}(itAx^{\alpha})) \\ &= \sin_{\alpha}(r \cos_{\alpha}(tAx^{\alpha}) + i \cdot r \sin_{\alpha}(tAx^{\alpha})) \\ &= \sin_{\alpha}(r \cos_{\alpha}(tAx^{\alpha})) \otimes_{\alpha} \cosh_{\alpha}(r \sin_{\alpha}(tAx^{\alpha})) + i \cdot \cos_{\alpha}(r \cos_{\alpha}(tAx^{\alpha})) \otimes_{\alpha} \sinh_{\alpha}(r \sin_{\alpha}(tAx^{\alpha})). \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

And

$$\begin{aligned} & \sin_{\alpha}(rE_{\alpha}(itAx^{\alpha})) \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{(2n+1)!} (rE_{\alpha}(itAx^{\alpha}))^{\otimes_{\alpha} (2n+1)} \quad (\text{by Eq. (15)}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{(2n+1)!} r^{2n+1} E_{\alpha}(i(2n+1)tAx^{\alpha}) \quad (\text{by matrix fractional DeMoivre's formula}) \\
&= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{(2n+1)!} r^{2n+1} [\cos_{\alpha}((2n+1)tAx^{\alpha}) + i \cdot \sin_{\alpha}((2n+1)tAx^{\alpha})]. \quad (\text{by matrix fractional Euler's formula})
\end{aligned}$$

It follows that

$$\sin_{\alpha}(r\cos_{\alpha}(tAx^{\alpha})) \otimes_{\alpha} \cosh_{\alpha}(r\sin_{\alpha}(tAx^{\alpha})) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{(2n+1)!} r^{2n+1} \cos_{\alpha}((2n+1)tAx^{\alpha}),$$

and

$$\cos_{\alpha}(r\cos_{\alpha}(tAx^{\alpha})) \otimes_{\alpha} \sinh_{\alpha}(r\sin_{\alpha}(tAx^{\alpha})) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{(2n+1)!} r^{2n+1} \sin_{\alpha}((2n+1)tAx^{\alpha}).$$

On the other hand, since

$$\begin{aligned}
&\cos_{\alpha}(rE_{\alpha}(itAx^{\alpha})) \\
&= \cos_{\alpha}(r\cos_{\alpha}(tAx^{\alpha}) + i \cdot r\sin_{\alpha}(tAx^{\alpha})) \\
&= \cos_{\alpha}(r\cos_{\alpha}(tAx^{\alpha})) \otimes_{\alpha} \cosh_{\alpha}(r\sin_{\alpha}(tAx^{\alpha})) - i \cdot \sin_{\alpha}(r\cos_{\alpha}(tAx^{\alpha})) \otimes_{\alpha} \sinh_{\alpha}(r\sin_{\alpha}(tAx^{\alpha})). \quad (25)
\end{aligned}$$

And

$$\begin{aligned}
&\cos_{\alpha}(rE_{\alpha}(itAx^{\alpha})) \\
&= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{(2n)!} (rE_{\alpha}(itAx^{\alpha}))^{\otimes_{\alpha} 2n} \quad (\text{by Eq. (14)}) \\
&= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{(2n)!} r^{2n} E_{\alpha}(i2ntAx^{\alpha}) \quad (\text{by matrix fractional DeMoivre's formula}) \\
&= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{(2n)!} r^{2n} [\cos_{\alpha}(2ntAx^{\alpha}) + i \cdot \sin_{\alpha}(2ntAx^{\alpha})]. \quad (\text{by matrix fractional Euler's formula})
\end{aligned}$$

It follows that

$$\cos_{\alpha}(r\cos_{\alpha}(tAx^{\alpha})) \otimes_{\alpha} \cosh_{\alpha}(r\sin_{\alpha}(tAx^{\alpha})) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{(2n)!} r^{2n} \cos_{\alpha}(2ntAx^{\alpha}),$$

and

$$\sin_{\alpha}(r\cos_{\alpha}(tAx^{\alpha})) \otimes_{\alpha} \sinh_{\alpha}(r\sin_{\alpha}(tAx^{\alpha})) = - \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{(2n)!} r^{2n} \sin_{\alpha}(2ntAx^{\alpha}). \quad \text{q.e.d.}$$

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we obtain the fractional Fourier series of four types of matrix fractional functions based on a new multiplication of fractional analytic functions. Matrix fractional Euler's formula and matrix fractional DeMoivre's formula play important roles in this article. In fact, our results are generalizations of classical calculus results. In the future, we will continue to study the problems in applied mathematics and fractional differential equations.

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